

BIOTRAILS

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

SOMMARIO

ABSTRACT	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. SEM METHOD FRAMEWORK	5
2.1 WHEN TO USE CB-SEM VS PLS-SEM: A GUIDE TO MODEL SELECTION	5
2.2 THE SEM DEVELOPMENT PROCESS.....	6
3. SEM ADAPTATION TO CASE STUDIES	8
3.1 GHANA GOLD CASE STUDY.....	9
3.2 GREEK AQUACULTURE CASE STUDY	9
3.3 GREEK FISHERIES CASE STUDY.....	10
4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS	11
4.1 METHOD AND DATA LIMITATIONS	11
4.2 LESSONS LEARNED	12
4.3 KEY REMARKS.....	12
REFERENCES	13

Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
SEM	Structural Equation Modelling
BCS	Biodiversity–Climate–Society
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
PLS-SEM	Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling
PBC	Perceived Behavioural Control
SDMs	System Dynamics Models
CB-SEM	Covariance-Based SEM
χ^2	Chi-square statistic
RMSEA	Root Mean Square Error of Approximation
CFI	Comparative Fit Index
TLI	Tucker–Lewis Index
SRMR	Standardized Root Mean Square Residual
R^2	Coefficient of Determination
Q^2	Predictive Relevance
f^2	Effect Size
HTMT	Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio of Correlations
CR	Composite Reliability
AVE	Average Variance Extracted
VIF	Variance Inflation Factor
NFI	Normed Fit Index

ABSTRACT

This technical publication presents the methodological framework and application of Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) within the BIOTRAILS project, focusing on three representative case studies: the Ghana gold supply chain, the Greek aquaculture and the Greek fisheries supply chains. The work was carried out under Task 3.2 and contributes to the operationalisation of the Biodiversity–Climate–Society (BCS) Nexus by quantifying behavioural determinants driving transformative change. SEM provides a practical method for understanding how stakeholders' norms, attitudes, and perceptions influence their intention to adopt biodiversity and climate mitigation friendly practices. The methodological approach applies the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) with a Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) approach to assess relationships among TPB variables namely, Attitude, Subjective Norms, Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC), and Intention. Findings across case studies demonstrate that PBC is the primary determinant of behavioural intention, reflecting the importance of institutional support, training, and enabling conditions in promoting sustainability transitions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The BIOTRAILS project co-developed a Nexus Framework for biodiversity-relevant transformative change through interdisciplinary models and participatory approaches. The project's methodological backbone connects social, ecological, and economic dimensions across multiple case studies, each representing different supply chains. Specifically, work Package 3 focuses on developing integrated models that capture the interactions among these dimensions, with Task 3.2 specifically addressing human behaviour and social norms as drivers of transformation. This report represents the technical process used to model human behavioural intention using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), providing the basis for integrating behavioural insights into System Dynamics Models (SDMs) developed under Task 3.5.

Behavioural models are essential to understand the social mechanisms that enable or hinder the adoption of biodiversity-relevant practices [1][10]. Decisions by individuals, producers, or institutions are shaped by complex interactions among beliefs, perceived control, social expectations, and available resources. Quantifying these relationships is critical for designing policies that foster transformative change, as it can reveal leverage points and points of intervention that can induce change. SEM provides a statistical framework for this purpose by combining elements of factor analysis and path analysis to represent causal relationships among observed and unobserved (latent) variables [7][8]. The approach used in BIOTRAILS allows us to test behavioural hypotheses grounded in the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) linking human behaviour to broader system components.

2. SEM METHOD FRAMEWORK

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) is a multivariate statistical method used to test complex cause-effect relationships between latent and manifest variables. It enables researchers to evaluate theoretical constructs that cannot be directly observed, such as attitudes, perceptions, or intentions, by linking them to measurable indicators. SEM combines two interdependent components: (i) the measurement model, which defines how observed indicators represent latent constructs, and (ii) the structural model, which specifies the relationships among those constructs [7]. Together, these models provide a broad representation of causal structures within complex systems.

2.1 WHEN TO USE CB-SEM VS PLS-SEM: A GUIDE TO MODEL SELECTION

Two major SEM paradigms exist: Covariance-Based SEM (CB-SEM) and Partial Least Squares SEM (PLS-SEM) [7]. CB-SEM, rooted in psychometrics, focuses on model fit and theory while PLS-SEM is variance-based and it prioritises predictive accuracy and model exploration. In detail, CB-SEM is primarily confirmatory, focusing on validating established theoretical frameworks through the optimization of model fit indices such as χ^2 , RMSEA, and CFI [7]. It requires large, normally distributed datasets and is best suited for well-defined relationships and theory-driven research (table 1). In contrast, PLS-SEM is variance-based and predictive, designed for exploratory analysis where theory is still evolving or data availability is limited. It can process small samples, non-normal distributions, and formative constructs, making it ideal for applied and transdisciplinary contexts such as the case studies within BIOTRAILS, where multiple social, environmental, and institutional factors interact. In fact, while CB-SEM seeks to confirm how well a model fits existing theory, PLS-SEM aims to maximise the explained variance of key constructs, providing stronger predictive power and practical insights for the supply chains studied [6].

Table 1: Comparison between CB-SEM and PLS-SEM method based on the study objectives and goals.

Criterion	Covariance-Based SEM (CB-SEM)	Partial Least Squares SEM (PLS-SEM)
Primary Objective	Confirmation and testing of established theory	Development and exploration of predictive models
Statistical Approach	Covariance-based (maximizes model fit between estimated and observed covariance matrices)	Variance-based (maximises explained variance of dependent constructs)
Modelling Approach	Confirmatory	Predictive/Exploratory
Assumptions	Requires multivariate normal data and large sample sizes ($100 < n < 200$)	No strict distribution assumptions; handles small samples effectively
Model Type	Reflective measurement models (indicators caused by latent constructs)	Reflective or formative (indicators can cause the construct)
Goal of Analysis	Minimizes difference between model-designed and observed covariance matrices (model fit)	Maximizes R^2 (variance explained) and prediction accuracy
Fit Indices used	χ^2 test, RMSEA, CFI, TLI, SRMR	SRMR, R^2 , Q^2 , f^2 , HTMT
Data Requirements	Large size, normally distributed, continuous data	Suitable for small to medium, non-normal distributions, categorical or ordinal data
Model Complexity	Difficulty in modelling many constructs or indicators	Handles complex models efficiently (many indicators/paths)
Error Handling	Focus on measurement errors and model fit	Focus on predictive accuracy and reliability of structural paths
Output Focus	Model validation and fit quality	Prediction, theory building, and exploratory research
When to Use	When theory is well-established and confirmatory testing is required	When theory is developing, data are limited, or model is complex

Since our sample size was relatively small and our data were categorical in nature, the PLS-SEM approach was considered more suitable, focusing on prediction accuracy and the reliability of structural paths. Subsequently, the goal was to maximise the explained variance of behavioural intention, making it particularly suitable for exploratory, real-world applications such as the BIOTRAILS gold, fisheries and aquaculture case studies. We have provided detailed information on the PLS-SEM approach in a prior BIOTRAILS deliverable [4].

2.2 THE SEM DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The SEM process follows a structured series of core steps that ensures the statistical robustness and theoretical validity of the model. Each step, from model specification to interpretation, builds upon the previous one to progressively translate theoretical assumptions into quantifiable relationships among latent and manifest variables. This systematic approach is crucial because it guarantees that constructs are accurately measured, data are rigorously tested, and causal pathways are empirically validated by the modeller. Through careful estimation and evaluation, the

process balances theoretical consistency with predictive power, allowing the identification of the most influential factors [8]. Essentially, these steps ensure that the resulting model is both methodologically robust and empirically meaningful, providing a reliable basis for explaining complex systems. The steps are as follows:

1. Model Specification

The initial step involves establishing a robust theoretical framework that delineates the hypothesised relationships among the latent constructs, thereby providing a conceptual foundation for the proposed model. Subsequently, it is necessary to describe the nature of the measurement models, distinguishing between reflective models, in which the indicators are manifestations of the underlying construct, and formative models, where the indicators collectively define and shape the construct. Following upon this, a comprehensive path model should be developed to depict the causal linkages among latent and manifest variables, offering a visual representation of the theoretical assumptions and guiding the empirical testing of the proposed relationships.

2. Data Collection and Preparation

The data collection process includes the design and distribution of structured questionnaires or surveys aimed at capturing measurable indicators of the latent constructs. Responses are systematically coded, typically employing 5-point Likert scales to ensure consistency and comparability across variables. To address issues of incomplete data, median imputation is applied for variables with missing values, except in cases where more than 30 percent of the data are missing, in which case the variable is excluded from further analysis. Following data collection, the dataset is standardised and cleaned, with diagnostic assessments conducted to evaluate normality and detect potential multicollinearity among the variables, thereby ensuring the integrity and reliability of the data for subsequent analysis.

3. Model Identification

Prior to model estimation, it is essential to verify that the proposed model is mathematically solvable by ensuring that the degrees of freedom are greater than or equal to zero. This assessment confirms the model's statistical feasibility and provides the basis for valid variable estimation. Furthermore, the model must be evaluated to determine whether it is under-identified, just-identified, or over-identified, as this classification directly influences the interpretability and reliability of the estimated parameters within the SEM framework.

4. Model Estimation

The estimation phase uses PLS-SEM algorithms to derive latent variable scores and estimate the corresponding path coefficients. This approach facilitates the simultaneous assessment of both measurement and structural relationships within the model. To evaluate the statistical significance of parameter estimates and the reliability of constructs, bootstrapping procedures (typically with 400 resamples) are conducted. In addition, the estimation process involves the computation of both outer (measurement) model parameters, which assesses the relationships between indicators and their respective constructs, and inner (structural) model parameters, which captures the hypothesised causal relationships among latent variables.

5. Measurement Model Evaluation (Outer Model)

The evaluation of the measurement model begins with the evaluation of indicator reliability, ensuring that factor loadings exceed the recommended threshold of 0.7, thereby confirming the adequacy of individual items in representing their respective constructs. Internal consistency is subsequently examined using Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability (CR), both of which should meet or surpass the conventional cutoff value of 0.7 to be acceptable. Convergent validity

is then established by calculating the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which should be greater than or equal to 0.5, indicating that the construct explains at least half of the variance in its indicators. Finally, discriminant validity is tested using both the Fornell–Larcker criterion and the Heterotrait–Monotrait ratio (HTMT), with HTMT values below 0.9 indicating satisfactory discriminant validity among the latent constructs.

6. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

The evaluation of the structural model involves examining the estimated path coefficients to determine the strength, direction, and statistical significance of the hypothesised relationships among latent constructs. Prior to interpreting these results, multicollinearity is assessed through the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), ensuring that all values remain below the acceptable threshold of 5 to confirm the independence of predictor variables. The model's explanatory power is then evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), while effect sizes (f^2) are calculated to assess the individual contribution of each predictor construct. Additionally, predictive relevance is verified through the Stone–Geisser Q^2 statistic, where values greater than zero indicate satisfactory predictive capability. Finally, overall model fit is assessed using the Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), which should be below 0.08, and the Normed Fit Index (NFI), which should exceed 0.9, thereby confirming the adequacy of the model in representing the observed data.

7. Model Refinement

In cases where the initial estimation results reveal non-significant structural paths, the model should be re-specified to enhance its empirical robustness and theoretical coherence. This process involves the systematic removal or refinement of problematic indicators and relationships, guided by both statistical criteria and theoretical justification. Following re-specification, the estimation and validation procedures are re-run iteratively until the model achieves a stable solution that is both statistically sound and theoretically consistent with the underlying conceptual framework.

8. Model interpretation and integration

The final stage involves the interpretation and integration of the model's empirical results. The significance, magnitude, and direction of the causal paths are examined to draw substantive conclusions regarding the hypothesised relationships among latent constructs. Comparative analysis may then be conducted across case studies or groups to identify patterns, differences, or contextual variations in the structural relationships. Results are visualised through comprehensive path diagrams that depict factor loadings, causal linkages, and the proportion of explained variance, facilitating in this way, clearer interpretation and communication of findings. Finally, the validated results are integrated into broader system-level frameworks, such as the BIOTRAILS System Dynamics Models, to provide a thorough understanding of the interdependencies and feedback mechanisms within the studied system across all case studies.

3. SEM ADAPTATION TO CASE STUDIES

In BIOTRAILS, SEM was used to uncover behavioural determinants underlying stakeholders' decisions within complex social-ecological systems, in particular, supply chains. Within BIOTRAILS, the theoretical foundation for SEM application lies in the Theory of Planned Behaviour which claims that behavioural intention is determined by three constructs: Attitude (the positive or negative evaluation of a behaviour), Subjective Norms (social pressures or expectations), and Perceived Behavioural Control (the perceived ease or difficulty of engaging in a behaviour) [1]. On the contrary, Intention predicts actual behaviour. The model was extended to include additional context-specific variables such as trust, social responsibility, and perceived institutional support, after the initial interviews with stakeholders took place (as described in detail in [3]) enhancing its relevance to governance and policymaking.

3.1 GHANA GOLD CASE STUDY

The Ghana Gold case study examined behavioural determinants among stakeholders involved in the small-scale mining sector. The PLS-SEM results demonstrate that Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) is the strongest and most significant predictor of behavioural intention ($\beta = 0.390$, $p < 0.01$), followed by Attitude ($\beta = 0.312$, $p = 0.039$), while Subjective Norms ($\beta = 0.180$, $p = 0.291$) were not significant. The model explained 60.2% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.602$) in behavioural intention and achieved a Goodness-of-Fit (GoF) = 0.5914, confirming robust predictive capability.

Analytically, the key manifest variables contributing to PBC included:

- PBC16.2: Lack of spatial planning
- PBC16.3: Training and information
- PBC16.7: Policies and regulators are not aligned or do not coordinate

For Attitude, the strongest loadings were linked to environmental degradation:

- Attitude6.6: Landscape quality degradation
- Attitude6.8: River baseflow reduction
- Attitude6.9: Riverbank erosion

Finally, the most influential Intention indicators were:

- Intention12.4: Family
- Intention12.5: Local traditions
- Intention12.6: Equality/Equity

These findings suggest that stakeholders' capacity, institutional coordination, and perceived control, rather than social influence, drive intention toward adopting biodiversity-friendly practices across the gold supply chain.

3.2 GREEK AQUACULTURE CASE STUDY

In the Greek Aquaculture sector, the PLS-SEM revealed that Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) is again the strongest and only statistically significant predictor of behavioural intention ($\beta = 0.470$, $p < 0.01$). Attitude ($\beta = 0.273$, $p = 0.166$) and Subjective Norms ($\beta = 0.037$, $p = 0.848$) showed no significant relationships, indicating that confidence in one's ability to act outweighs belief or perceived social pressure. The model explained 41.9% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.419$) and achieved a GoF = 0.4799, indicating a moderately strong and stable fit.

The strongest manifest variables for PBC were:

- PBC16.1: Education and information
- PBC16.2: Consumer information & awareness
- PBC20.6: Waste recycling

For Intention, two key items dominated:

- Intention11.4: Certification
- Intention11.7: Long-term sustainability goals

The f^2 effect sizes further underscore this pattern:

- ❖ PBC → Intention: 0.188 (medium contribution)
- ❖ Attitude → Intention: 0.084 (small to medium contribution)
- ❖ Subjective Norms → Intention: 0.015 (negligible contribution)

Overall, the results confirm that behavioural change within aquaculture is largely shaped by individuals perceived control, particularly their access to education, information, and recycling practices, rather than attitude or normative factors.

3.3 GREEK FISHERIES CASE STUDY

The Greek Fisheries model, derived from 29 participants, presents a slightly different behavioural dynamic. While Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) remains the strongest overall influence, its significance is marginal ($\beta = 0.384$, $p = 0.0564$), whereas Attitude ($\beta = 0.363$, $p = 0.0172$) emerged as a statistically significant determinant of intention. Subjective Norms ($\beta = -0.225$, $p = 0.2270$) were not significant, showing once again the limited role of social pressure. The model explains 56.4% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.564$) in Intention, with GoF = 0.5731, indicating good fit and strong explanatory power.

The key manifest variables defining Attitude include:

- Attitude4.4: Eutrophication
- Attitude4.3: Overuse of vaccines/medicines
- Attitude4.7: Changes in the dynamics of species

For PBC, significant variables were:

- PBC13.4: Lack of partnerships
- PBC18.3: Informing and training employees
- PBC16.1: Education and information

Effect sizes (f^2) further confirm these relationships:

- ❖ PBC → Intention: 0.384 (large contribution)
- ❖ Attitude → Intention: 0.363 (medium contribution)
- ❖ Subjective Norms → Intention: 0.225 (small contribution)

These results suggest that individual awareness and perceptions of biodiversity loss (Attitude), combined with the stakeholders perceived knowledge capacity, training, and institutional collaboration (PBC), are the key behavioural determinants for transformation in the fisheries sector.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The BIOTRAILS SEM framework established a methodological connection between behavioural determinants and systems modelling, providing a quantifiable way to understand the human dimension within the BCS Nexus. The validated results demonstrate that PBC is the most statistically significant determinant of behavioural intention across the Ghana and Aquaculture case studies, highlighting the importance of institutional alignment and access to knowledge and training, as enabling factors for transformative change. In contrast, Attitude plays a notable role mostly in the fisheries sector, where cultural identity, environmental awareness, and personal responsibility are more likely to shape stakeholders' willingness to adopt biodiversity conservation relevant practices. Subjective norms remain weak and statistically insignificant in all three cases, suggesting that social pressure has limited influence on behavioural adoption compared to attitude and perceived control. Overall, these findings confirm that behavioural change within biodiversity-relevant systems emerges from a dynamic interplay between agency (PBC) and value orientation (Attitude) rather than normative formulations. Integrating these behavioural insights into System Dynamics Models (SDMs) allows BIOTRAILS to more accurately simulate how social factors interact with these systems, identifying leverage points where key transformative change processes can be effectively triggered.

4.1 METHOD AND DATA LIMITATIONS

Despite strong internal consistency, several methodological limitations should be acknowledged. These are listed below:

- a. Sample size: The number of respondents per case (29-44) limits statistical power and external validity, especially for multi-group or sector-specific comparisons. Although PLS-SEM accommodates small samples, broader datasets would improve the credibility of the results.
- b. Data validity: The reliance on self-reported answers introduces subjective bias, particularly in sensitive topics like environmental responsibility and compliance behaviour [9]. Future surveys should incorporate multiple data sources with observational or secondary data e.g., using existing datasets or records, such as policy documents, production statistics, or environmental monitoring data, to compare with what participants report.
- c. Response bias: Some stakeholders, particularly institutional actors, may overemphasize positive intentions either out of social desirability or a sense of affiliation with the project, a pattern observed from some policymakers during the workshops [5]. For instance, a policymaker might say they strongly support biodiversity conservation even if their actions or priorities don't fully reflect that, since such an answer seems more acceptable in a research or workshop setting. Weighting schemes or bias-correction techniques could mitigate this effect in future research [9].
- d. Cross-case comparisons: While the models share core constructs, contextual differences in governance, culture, and market dynamics mean that coefficients are not directly comparable across all case studies we examined. However, the aquaculture and fisheries cases share similar institutional mechanisms and distribution channels which makes them more suitable for direct comparison.
- e. Static vs dynamic models: The models capture static representations of relationships in

time based on two stages of data collection through surveys. Behavioural dynamics are likely to evolve in the future especially in cases (e.g., aquaculture farms) where innovation and technology or market structure evolves at a fast pace [2]. Additional rounds of surveys could contribute to the representation of evolving relationships, behaviours and social dynamics.

Addressing these limitations in another stage, through additional samples, repeated surveys, and a larger integration with market data, will likely enhance the explanatory power of the BIOTRAILS behavioural framework.

4.2 LESSONS LEARNED

Applying SEM within BIOTRAILS revealed several key lessons. Context-specificity matters greatly, as behavioural constructs vary across socio-cultural and institutional settings, requiring flexible model design and refinement. Strengthening institutional capacity, training and information emerged as core leverage points, while aligning policy measures with local values enhances adoption of sustainable practices, especially in attitude-driven systems such as the Greek fisheries sector. In parallel, the stakeholder validation workshop improved model credibility and ensured real-world relevance. However, additional rounds of surveys and workshops could refine further the SEM variables to achieve increased explanatory power.

4.3 KEY REMARKS

In summary, the SEM approach within BIOTRAILS has demonstrated its capacity to disentangle the human dimensions underlying sustainability transitions. While methodological and data availability challenges remain, the results deliver actionable insights into how attitudes, perceived control, and enabling conditions can drive biodiversity-friendly behaviours. Integrating SEM outputs with System Dynamics Models proved essential for connecting behavioural insights with systemic feedback, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of transformation pathways. In this way, BIOTRAILS contributes to identifying effective leverage points for transformative change that are empirically grounded, stakeholder validated, and policy relevant.

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